

RAMAN SPECTRA OF SUBSTITUTED SULPHURIC ACIDS. PART I.

BY JAGANNATH GUPTA AND ANIL KUMAR MAJUMDAR.

The Raman spectra of $\text{NH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ and $\text{NH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{Na}$ have been photographed under different conditions. It is found that the tetrahedral structure of the sulphates persists in the amino derivative. Force constants have been calculated and their significance discussed.

Interesting differences in the Raman spectra of sulphates and bisulphates were observed by previous workers (Nisi, *Jap. J. Phys.*, 1929, 8, 119; Woodward, *Physikal. Z.*, 1931, 32, 777) which might be due to differences of small magnitude in the ionic structures. The present investigation has been taken up with the purpose of studying the effect of partial and gradual substitution in the sulphato group on its structural characteristics. Houlton and Tartar's work on the Raman spectra of ethyl and higher alkyl sulphonates and sulphinates (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 544) show the effect of alkyl substitution, although data on the methyl derivative are lacking. The effect of substitution by amino groups is the object of study of the present work.

The simplest amino derivative of sulphuric acid is aminosulphonic acid ($\text{NH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H}$), which forms stable, colourless, anhydrous crystals at room temperatures, and is now well known as a very suitable primary acidimetric standard. Conductometric and pH measurements (Sakurai, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 1654; Cupery, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1938, 30, 627) indicate that it is quite a strong acid, comparable to sulphuric acid itself.

At ordinary temperatures, an aqueous solution of the acid is quite stable, appreciable hydrolysis being detectable after a week. Alkaline solutions, however, slowly hydrolyse to sulphates. In all cases decomposition is favoured by a rise of temperature.

The Raman spectra of the acid and its sodium salt have been examined under different conditions, the results of which are reported in the present paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The acid was easily prepared by the action of fuming sulphuric acid on urea (Baumgarten, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 1929). The precipitated crystals were purified by recrystallisation from water (m.p. 205°). A large single crystal (measuring $12 \times 9 \times 3$ mm.) was prepared by slow evaporation of

the aqueous solution and kindly lent to us by Dr. P. B. Sarkar. The faces of this crystal were polished by carefully rubbing it on a piece of moist cloth, and were protected by coating with a thin layer of white vaseline. An exposure of 24 hours with the unfiltered radiation from a quartz-mercury arc lamp yielded a fairly intense spectrum.

Solvents used for examining the solutions were all freshly distilled before work. The aqueous solutions (50%) were repeatedly filtered directly into the Wood's tube to obtain it free from suspended impurities. The methyl alcoholic solution (25%) of the acid was filtered through a glass-sintered gooch crucible instead of through a filter paper. Each solution was qualitatively tested before and after exposure, which varied from 24 to 40 hours, and found free from sulphate. In examining the solutions, the radiations from the mercury arc were filtered through a 4% solution of *m*-dinitrobenzene in benzene to cut off the 4047Å group of lines. In spite of all attempts, the spectrum of the alcoholic solution was unsatisfactory, due to a strong continuous background masking the Raman lines. The results are given in the following table.

TABLE I.

(Raman lines in cm.^{-1})P=polarised. $\rho \ll 0.5$; D=completely depolarised

Crystal.	Aq. soln.	ρ .	Soln. in MeOH (incomplete)	Sodium sulphamate (aq. soln.).
352 (2b)	380 (2)	D		393 (1)
535 (2)				570 (1)
550 (2)	545 (3)	D		
677 (1)				
604 (1)	714 (1)	D		
1054 (5b)	1072 (6)	P	1068 (1)	969 (1)
1271 (1)	1310 (4)	D		1037 (2)
3080-3180 (2b)				

Figures in paranthesis indicate approximate relative intensities estimated visually. With a standard polarisation set-up, using a Wollaston prism, the spectrum of the acid solution was photographed to ascertain the polarisation characteristics of the lines qualitatively, and the results are shown in column 3, Table I.

DISCUSSION.

It may be observed that the spectra of the acid and its salt are similar but not identical, and do not agree on many points with those recorded previously by Angus, Leckie and Williams (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, **34**, 793). The line at 1357 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the acid is very weak and completely vanishes in that of the salt, and is therefore attributed to a deformation vibration of the hydroxy group. Among the other lines recorded, it may be remarked that the difference between the spectra of the acid and its salt is less than that between sulphuric acid and sulphates of the same concentrations (*cf.* Hibben, *Chem. Rev.*, 1933, **13**, 404), but is greater than that between the bisulphates and sulphates (Fadda, *Nuovo cimento*, 1932, **9**, 168). Polarisation photograph shows that in the solution of the acid, the intense line at 1065 cm^{-1} is highly polarised, while the rest are completely depolarised. These observations indicate that the structure of the sulphamic acid molecule is essentially tetrahedral, and is not greatly changed in the formation of the ionised salt, although minor distortions in structure are quite probable. The large shift of one of the three-fold degenerates (ν_3) from 714 in the acid to 969 in the salt is remarkable, the spectrum of the latter being a closer approach to that of the sulphate.

The force constants of the tetrahedral molecules of the acid and its salt have accordingly been calculated using the central force system (*cf.* Kohlrausch, *S.R.E.*, 1931, p. 213), the reasonable assumption being made that the valence forces of the central sulphur atom are identical. The results obtained lend support to this assumption of complete identity of the purely co-valent link S-NH₂ and the co-ordination links with the oxygen atoms, since the spectrum resembles that of a regular tetrahedron rather than of a symmetrical top. In Table II have been tabulated these constants along with that obtained from the data of allied substances.

TABLE II.

	$f \times 10^{-5}$.	$f \times 10^{-5}$.
SO ₂	4.6	1.14
HSO ₄ ⁻	4.5	1.47
NH ₂ SO ₃ ⁻	4.93	1.31
NH ₂ SO ₃ H	4.07	1.67

If on the strength of the results obtained with the sulphate and the bisulphate ions, it is assumed that a distortion of the regular tetrahedron is marked by a falling off of the central force and a corresponding increase in the deformation constant, it follows that the aminosulphonate ion is a more regular tetrahedron than the free acid. It is, however, usually found that in perfectly regular tetrahedral molecules, $\nu_3 > \nu_1$, while the opposite is being observed here. A permanent departure from a regular tetrahedral structure may not therefore be improbable in aminosulphonic acid and to a lesser degree in its anion. It may also be observed that in the spectrum of the crystal of the acid, some of the degenerates are split up due probably to the anisotropic field of the distorted tetrahedra.

The case for the formation of a protropic isomer of aminosulphonic acid of the type $\text{NH}_3^+\text{SO}_3^-$ is not clear from the optical data available up till now, although the possibility is by no means excluded. Infra-red absorption at 3.15μ is often identified with the NH_2 group, but is seen to persist in glycine where the group presumably becomes NH_3^+ ; the sulphamic acid crystal shows absorption at 3.17μ (Buswell, Downing and Rodebush, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 2759), on which observation therefore any deduction regarding proton shifting is uncertain. In the Raman spectrum of the anhydrous crystal examined by us, a broad band at $3080\text{--}3180\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been observed, which must be due to hydrogen oscillations against nitrogen or oxygen. The O-H frequencies are known to be in close proximity to the N-H and to suffer large deviations in value depending on the state and structure of the molecule; e.g., water shows a very broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} which shifts to 3100 cm^{-1} in ice (Sutherland, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, **141A**, 535). The broad band at $3080\text{--}3180\text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed in the acid crystal may, on the other hand, indicate the formation of an NH_3^+ ion as was pointed out by Edsall (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, **5**, 225) in his study of the organic amine hydrochlorides.

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